

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP

"MOUNTAIN ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE AND MIGRATION"

Hybrid – online & in-person

January 22, 2024, Madrid, SPAIN

Registration of the participants	12.00-12.30
Event welcome	12.30-12.45
Plenary speakers	12.45-14.00
<i>BRINDUSA STERPU, Centre for Mountain Economy & CBM International University</i> <i>Economic Resilience and Vulnerability in the Face of Climatic Shifts: An In-depth Analysis of the Impacts of Climate Change on Mountainous Economies</i>	12.45-13.15
<i>MIHAI COVACI, Hyperion Universty & CBM International University</i> <i>Dynamics of Rural-to-Urban Migration: Analyzing the Multifaceted Phenomenon of Population Shifts</i>	13.15-13.45
Q & A	13.45-14.00
Parallel sessions	14.00-15.00
<i>Session 1 - Climate change in Science, Art, and Humanity</i> <i>EVA CLARK, Akademos Learning UK</i> <i>The Altered Intersection: Exploring the Transformative Nexus of Climate Change on the Interplay Between Art and Science</i>	14.00-14.30
<i>ALBERT LEWIS, 9472-9655 Quebec Canada</i> <i>Climate Change's Complex Interplay with the Scientific Landscape: A Mountain Comprehensive Exploration</i>	14.30-15.00
<i>Session 2 - Migration and depopulation, with local and regional focus</i> <i>JACK BAILEY, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences</i>	14.00-14.30

<p><i>Austria</i></p> <p><i>Dynamic Interconnections: Migration Patterns and their Impact on the Local Development Dynamics in Mountainous Regions</i></p> <p><i>OLIVIA CAMPBELL, Zealandina Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Demographic Shifts and their Implications for Regional Sustainability: A Comprehensive Examination of Depopulation Trends</i></p>	14.30-15.00
<p>Coffee break</p>	15.00-15.15
<p><i>Session 1 - Climate change in Science, Art, and Humanity</i></p> <p><i>CARLA SELMA, Akademos Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Mountainous Migration Dynamics: Unraveling the Complexities of Population Movements in Elevated Terrains</i></p> <p><i>PARVATI AARAV, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>The Interdisciplinary Nexus: Exploring the Multifaceted Impacts of Climate Change on the Interrelation of Science, Art, and Human Societies</i></p>	15.15-15.45 15.45-16.15
<p><i>Session 2 - Migration and depopulation, with local and regional focus</i></p> <p><i>LASHMI DURGA, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Dynamic Population Shifts: Exploring the Nexus of Migration and Depopulation with Emphasis on Local and Regional Perspectives</i></p> <p><i>SHI CHEN, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Navigating Demographic Transformations: A Comprehensive Inquiry into the Intricacies of Population Dynamics, Emphasizing Local and Regional Perspectives on Migration and Depopulation Interconnections.</i></p>	15.15-15.45 15.45-16.15
<p>Q&A</p>	16.15-16.45
<p>Concluding remarks</p>	16.45-17.00

Location: Rivas Square Garden, Calle Marie Curie, 9, 4ª Planta, 28521 Rivas-Vacia, Madrid, Spain (Indications: Rivas Futura Subway, Auditorio Miguel Rios)